

PERIODIC ACID AND PERIODATES. THE TERNARY SYSTEM SILVER OXIDE — PERIODIC ACID — WATER AT 0°.

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The reaction between silver oxide and periodic acid in presence of water only has been quantitatively studied at 0°. Three distinct salts, viz. $5\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7$, $2\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are found to be formed. Some properties of these compounds are recorded. The first two have been isolated in a pure condition.

While studying the 35° isotherm of the ternary system silver oxide-periodic acid-water (appearing elsewhere) it was observed that the compound $2\text{Ag}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{I}_2\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, which is red, did not form immediately on mixing suitable proportions of the three components. Instead, a straw-yellow powder was obtained which required over 24 hours to change into the red compound. This was at first suspected to be due to the action of light, specially in view of the fact that silver salts were involved. Subsequent experiments, however, showed that this was not the case. The change occurred in the dark also. It was therefore considered useful to study the system at a lower temperature, 0°, at which the straw-yellow compound was stable.

EXPERIMENTAL

With comparatively dilute solutions of periodic acid the arrangement shown in Fig. 1 was used. A was an elongated bulb of pyrex glass carrying a long stem B

and a side-tube C. The capacity of the bulb was about 100 c.c. and it was made somewhat irregular in shape to break up froth. C was attached to a guard vessel D which

in turn was joined to a water pump. An inner tube E of pyrex glass nearly reached the bottom of the bulb and was attached to it by means of a piece of rubber tubing F. To E were attached in series a soda-lime tube G and a washbottle H containing sulphuric acid. The bulb B was kept in a Dewar vessel K packed with crushed ice. The mixtures to be studied were made up by taking varying proportions of the three components. The mixtures were introduced into the bulb one at a time. On starting the pump a current of CO₂-free, dry air was drawn through the bulb which served to keep the mixture thoroughly agitated. After allowing sufficient time for equilibrium to be attained (3 or 4 days), the solid was allowed to settle. The saturated solution and the wet residue were then analysed as described in previous papers (*loc. cit.*).

With mixtures containing a large excess of periodic acid (which necessitated the use of smaller volumes of water) the arrangement used was that employed for the determination of solubility of periodic acid in water at 0°. The mixture was introduced into a small bulb and sealed as before prior to mechanical shaking (cf. Gyani and Gyani, this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 239).

The results of the analyses of the various saturated solutions and the corresponding wet residues are given in Table I. The first column gives the amount of Ag₂O and the second that of the acid calculated as I₂O₇, for the solution. The next two columns give the corresponding amounts in the wet residue. The amount of acid has been expressed in terms of I₂O₇, for reasons given in the previous paper.

TABLE I

Silver oxide-periodic acid-water at 0°.

Percentages by weight				Solid phase
Solutions		Wet residues		
Ag ₂ O.	I ₂ O ₇ .	Ag ₂ O.	I ₂ O ₇ .	
Traces	Traces	31.28	8.15	Ag ₂ O+5Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇
„	0.0235	19.70	6.32	5Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇
„	0.0252	25.82	8.27	
0.0016	0.0306	19.09	12.88	5Ag ₂ O I ₂ O ₇ +2Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .3H ₂ O
0.0025	1.321	17.00	14.16	2Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .3H ₂ O
0.0039	13.07	13.34	20.31	
0.0064	21.87	15.06	27.67	
0.0175	35.48	12.76	37.03	
0.0236	39.13	15.77	39.76	
0.0456	49.71	19.29	50.48	2Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .3H ₂ O+Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .4H ₂ O
0.0463	49.73	22.46	51.79	
0.0398	52.11	16.71	53.11	Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .4H ₂ O
0.0409	57.77	18.96	56.29	
0.0203	60.95	16.47	57.93	
Traces	62.53	2.33	69.75	Ag ₂ O.I ₂ O ₇ .4H ₂ O+I ₂ O ₇ .5H ₂ O
—	62.51	—	—	I ₂ O ₇ .5H ₂ O

DISCUSSION

The results obtained in the above experiments are shown graphically in Fig. 2.

FIG. 2

It will be observed that the ternary saturation curves of the different solid phases lie so close to the $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ edge of the diagram that they practically coincide with it. Fig. 3 expresses the same results but has been drawn out of proportion so as to make the different saturation curves distinguishable. Thus, for example, the point A representing the saturated solution of Ag_2O in water should occur very close to the H_2O -vertex but has been shown considerably removed from it. Be-

sides the ternary saturation curves AB and EI' for Ag_2O and I_2O_7 , respectively, which are far too small to be experimentally realised, there are three more curves in Fig. 3,

namely, BC, CD and DE. The curve BC, points on which represent solutions containing between 0.00 and 0.0306% I_2O_7 , is also small and corresponds to a solid binary compound whose composition is represented by the formula $5\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ (point G in Fig. 3). Curve CD, which extends between 0.0306 and 49.72% I_2O_7 , is the saturation curve for the ternary compound $2\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ represented by the point H. Curve DE, which lies in a still more acidic region, namely, between 49.72 and 62.51% I_2O_7 , that is, up to the saturation point of periodic acid, corresponds to a ternary compound, $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (point K).

FIG. 3

The compound $5\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ is the same as that obtained at 35° . The compound $2\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a straw yellow powder. The compound $\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is a white crystalline solid.

The compound $5\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7$ was found to be stable in contact with water as was the case at 35° . It was therefore readily obtained in a pure state. Analysis of the compound confirmed its composition. $2\text{Ag}_2\text{O}\cdot\text{I}_2\text{O}_7\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is not stable in contact

with water the reason for which is clear from Fig. 3. For the isolation of this compound advantage has, however, been taken of the fact that it is capable of existence in contact with a very dilute solution of periodic acid, whose concentration is represented by the point C, namely, a solution containing 0.03% I_2O_7 (cf. $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot H_2O$ at 35°). The compound $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$ was therefore washed with a solution of this particular strength obtained by washing a little of the compound $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$ till the solid phase contained a mixture of this compound and $5Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7$ at 0° . It was dried over $CaCl_2$ at 0° and analysed. (Found: Ag_2O , 52.15; I_2O_7 , 41.16. $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$ requires Ag_2O , 52.47; I_2O_7 , 41.41 per cent). The compound $Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 4H_2O$, as can be seen from Fig. 3, is capable of stable existence only in contact with very concentrated solutions of periodic acid. The isolation of this compound is therefore difficult, more so, because it has a tendency to change on slight elevation of temperature. The compound $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$, when heated in an air-oven at 105° - 110° , at first turned black and then gradually became chocolate. The total loss of weight on heating was 7.77%, while dehydration according to the equation

requires a loss of 6.12%. It is interesting to note that the difference of 1.55% between the observed and calculated values is of the same order as observed in the case of the compound $2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot H_2O$, namely, 1.65%.

The properties of the different compounds obtained at the two temperatures are conveniently summarised in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Formula	Physical properties.	Stability.
1.	$5Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7$ ($Ag_5I_5O_8$?)	Black crystalline solid	Stable both at 0° and 35° . Stands washing with water. Can be obtained pure and dry.
2.	$2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot H_2O$ ($Ag_4I_2O_9 \cdot H_2O$?)	Shining chocolate crystals	Stable at 35° in contact with dilute periodic acid containing 0.07 to 50% I_2O_7 .
3.	$Ag_7O \cdot I_2O_7$	Canary-yellow crystals	Stable at 35° in contact with periodic acid containing over 50% I_2O_7 . On washing it changes into (2) then into (1). Stable at 0° in contact with acid solutions containing about 1 to 40% I_2O_7 . On washing it changes into (1). At 35° it changes into (2).
4.	$2Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O$	Straw-yellow powder	
5.	$Ag_2O \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 4H_2O$	Colorless crystals	Stable at 0° in contact with acid solutions containing over 52% I_2O_7 . With slight elevation of temperature it changes into (3).

Further work on these compounds is in progress.

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